

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF THE BRITTLE MATRIX LAYERED COMPOSITE REINFORCED BY SHORT FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Experimentally were fabricated layered fiberconcrete beams with different short fibers concentrations in layers and beams with fibers chaotically distributed in the volume. Beams were tested under four point bending conditions. Tests were shown, samples with non-homogeneous fiber distribution had higher load bearing capacity comparing with the samples having chaotically distributed fibers in all volume. Numerical model of layered structure having short fibers in plies simultaneously was elaborated. Each macro-crack opening is governing by pull-out process of fibers which are bridging the particular crack. The pull-out force for every single fiber was obtained experimentally performing single fiber pull-out tests. For this purpose experimental program was realized and pull-out force versus pull-out fiber length was obtained (for fibers embedded into a concrete at different depth and under different angle). Steel fibers were used. Fibers distribution in plies (and in the whole prism volume, for prism having chaotically distributed in the volume short fibers) was simulated using Monte-Carlo procedure. Depending on macro-crack size and opening, different crack parts (along the macro-crack) are bearing different load. If the load carried by each fiber at a constant crack opening is known from micro-mechanical investigation, the corresponding total bending load for a beam (or plate) was obtained through equilibrium conditions. Modeling results comparison with experimental data was allowed to recognize novel micro-mechanical failure mechanism in brittle matrix composites reinforced by short fibers, in the case of fibers concentration increase.

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel fiber reinforced concrete SFRC is a composite material with matrix- the homogeneous concrete and reinforcement - steel fibers. Addition of short, discontinuous fiber had played an important role in the improvement of many mechanical properties of concrete. Fiber reinforced concrete offer increased toughness, durability, impact resistance and control the initiation and growth of cracks. Investigating of mechanical properties of high-strength steel fiber reinforced concrete [1] have marked that brittleness explained by low tensile rupture strain of high strength concrete can be overcome by addition of steel fibers [2-6]. Nowadays, conventional steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) is mostly applied in the field of industrial floors with dosages fiber mass ranging from 20 to 80 kg/m³. Traditionally fibers are homogeneously dispersed in a concrete. At the same time in many situations fiberconcrete with homogeneously dispersed fibers is not optimal (majority of added fibers

are not participated in the loads bearing process). It's obvious that is possible to create construction having non-homogeneous fibers distribution in it in different ways. Few technologies were described in Latvian invention patents: Nr. LV14257 "Technology process and device for manufacturing fiberconcrete non-homogeneous structural elements" [7], LV14667 "Method for oriented reinforcement of fiberconcrete structures prior to concreting" [8] and Nr. LV14684 "Method for orienting fibers in fiber reinforced concrete" [9]. Present research examines the behaviour of composite steel fiber reinforced concrete beams with non-homogeneous fibers distribution in them. Layered beams with layers having different short fibers content in plies were fabricated (prisms were with dimensions 100×100×400 mm) according to technology [7]. Beams were tested under four point bending conditions. Beams post-cracking behavior was modelled numerically. For this reason numerical model of layered structure having short fibers in plies was elaborated. Each macro-crack opening is governing by pull-out process of fibers which are bridging the crack. Each single fiber pull-out force was obtained experimentally performing single fiber pull-out tests. For this purpose single fiber pull-out experimental program was realized and pull-out force versus pull-out fiber length was obtained (for fibers embedded into concrete at different depth and under different angle). Steel fibers were used. Fibers distribution in plies (and in the whole prism volume, for prism having chaotically distributed in the volume short fibers) was simulated using Monte-Carlo procedure. Numerically obtained load –deflection curves were compared with obtained in experiments.

2 LAYERED BEAMS FABRICATION

Non-homogeneous short fibers distribution in FRC structural elements may be organized in different ways. One option is to create plies with short fibers according to technology described in Latvian patent LV14257.

Concrete ingredients were place into the concrete mixer, where they were mixed, without water and plasticizer. After dry ingredients proper mixing, water and plasticizer were added and mix was mixed till the moment of reaching the liquid condition. In the case of SFRC with homogeneous fibers distribution, steel fibers were added and mix was mixed till the homogeneous statement. In the case of SFRC with non-homogeneous fibers distribution fibers were placed into the structural element body in ways will be described below. Commercially available end-hooked steel fibers Dramix RC 80/30BP were used in experiments. Used steel fibers had a relatively high tensile strength 1100 N/mm. Compression strength of concrete according to the performed test results (averaging for ten samples), was 73.1 MPa.

Liquid concrete was evenly poured into a mould forming the layer of constant thickness. Then fixed quantity of short fibers were scattered over its surface. According to the patent LV14257, fibers were pressed into the layer body by the steel grid or the roller made out of steel disks, adding vibrations (see fig. 1) [7].

Figure 1: Devices were used for fibers pressing into the concrete - steel grid or the roller made out of steel disks

In figures 2 – 4 are shown geometry of eight differently made layered samples groups, while the total amount of fibers is identical for all eight groups of specimens and it was 60 kg/m^3 , the difference only was in their distribution. Ten identical prisms of each type of fiber reinforced concrete were prepared, totally 80 samples. Specimen of Group 1 consists of fiber reinforced concrete with fibers homogeneously dispersed in the sample volume, these prisms were used as reference. For the specimens from Groups 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 moulds were gradually filled with the concrete mix according to the description of each group.

Figure 2: Fibers distribution in the samples of Groups 1,2 and 3

Figure 3: Fibers distribution in the samples of Groups 4, 5 and 6

Figure 4: Fibers distribution in the samples of Groups 7 and 8

Group No.2. Mould was filled by a concrete till 25 mm depth, then – $2/3$ of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was distributed over the concrete layer surface and was pressed into the layer covering whole thickness of the concrete layer 25 mm. Then concrete was added into the mould till the total depth 50 mm and next – $1/3$ of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete till the depth 25 mm. 50 mm of the concrete without fibers was added into the mould (see figure 2). Group No.3. Mould was filled by a concrete till 25 mm depth, then – $2/3$ of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete covering whole thickness of the concrete layer 25 mm. 75mm of the concrete without fibers was added into the mould and – $1/3$ of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was distributed and was pressed into a concrete on the depth 25 mm (see figure 2). Group No.4. Mould was filled by a concrete till 25 mm depth, then – $1/2$ of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was added covering whole thickness of the concrete layer 25 mm. Then concrete was added into the mould till the total depth 50 mm and next – $1/2$ of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete till the depth 25 mm. 50 mm of a concrete without fibers was added into the mould (see figure 3). Group No.5. Mould was filled by a concrete till 25 mm depth, then – $2/3$ of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into concrete covering whole thickness of the concrete layer 25

mm. Then concrete was added into the mould till the total depth 50 mm and next – 1/3 of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete till the depth 25 mm. 25 mm of a concrete without fibers were added into the mould (see figure 3). Group No.6. Mould was filled by a concrete till 55 mm depth, then all fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete till the depth 25 mm. 45 mm of a concrete without fibers were added into the mould (see figure 3). Group No.7. Mould was filled by a concrete till 25 mm depth, then – 1/3 of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete covering whole thickness of the concrete layer 25 mm. Mould was filled by a concrete till 25 mm depth, then – 1/3 of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into concrete covering whole thickness of the concrete

Fig. 5: a) Averaged load – beam middle point vertical deflection curves (for deflection range 0-2 mm); b) Layered sample after testing.

layer 25 mm. Mould was filled by concrete till 25 mm depth, then – 1/3 of the total amount of fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete covering whole thickness of the concrete layer 25 mm. 25 mm of concrete without fibers was added into the mould (see figure 4). Group No.8. Mould was filled by a concrete till 25 mm depth, then all fibers (60 kg/m^3) was uniformly distributed on the surface of the concrete in the mould and was pressed into the concrete till the depth 25 mm. 75 mm of a concrete without fibers were added into the mould (see figure 4).

3 BEAMS TESTING

Beams were tested under four point bending conditions. During loading each beam was cracked at its middle part and its future load bearing mechanism was provided only by pulling out short fibers which were bridged the crack crossing beam's crosssection. Both the beam vertical deflection, as well as the crack opening was measured during loading. Diagrams force – the middle point of prism vertical deflection are given in figure 5 for all types of prisms. Each curve was obtained performing testing results averaging for nine specimens. Three stages are seen in each curve; first of them is linear elastic (deflection from 0 to 0.01 mm). In this stage the fiber reinforced concrete prisms become deformed without visible cracks openings. In this stage micro cracks in a concrete are accumulating and growing, forming a macro-crack network. Macro cracks are oriented perpendicularly to the longitudinal axis of a prism. The density of the macro crack network depends on the specimen's geometry, size of fibers and their amount. Fibers traversing the macro cracks begin to bear load, while the cracks are still invisible on the outer surface of a specimen.

It proceeds the following way: fibers bearing load detach from the concrete and start to pull out one or both ends out of a concrete matrix. The individual load carrying capacity of the each fiber depends on its orientation towards the crack plane and how far it is extracted.

The next stage begins with deviation of curves from the straight line and terminates reaching the maximum value on curve with deflection of prisms equal to 0.5 mm – 1 mm, this stage is characterized by intensive cracking of the concrete matrix. The third stage is characterized by the decline of the total load carrying capacity of fiber. At this stage for all groups samples were observed single macro-crack at the middle part of the each prism. Crack was bridged by fibers and was slowly opened during increasing of external applied loads. Load bearing capacity of the each beam decreases proportionally to the size of the crack opening. The large amount of fibers (in some plies) leads to stress concentration and overload of the concrete matrix which leads to spalling of the concrete. Experimental observation of fiber pull-out micromechanics [10-14] shown that the maximum load carrying capacity of fiber depends on the orientation of fiber towards the direction of extraction force and how much the fiber has been extracted.

It can be observed, that samples from the Group 1 (reference specimens) were reached lower average load carrying capacity in the third stage (macro crack opening) compared to the specimens with the non-homogeneous distribution of fibers. Certain similar tendencies can be observed among the diagrams of the average results of the specimens – the maximal load carrying capacity is reached with deflection of prisms 0.75 mm – 1 mm, which correlates with the crack opening size. Group 8 reaches the highest load carrying capacity during the crack opening stage 0.1 – 1.1 mm due to the highest concentration of fibers compared to other groups in the lower part of the prism which bears the maximum tensile load. Layered sample fracture surface after testing is shown in figure 5 b.

3 SINGLE FIBER PULL-OUT MICROMECHANICS STUDY

Detailed experimental single fiber pull-out investigation was performed. Single steel fiber-concrete samples (see figure 6 a) were prepared and were tested in order to determine fiber pull-out resistance. Three different embedded lengths have been used in the investigation – 15 mm (symmetrical embedding of 30 mm long fiber), 10 mm and 5 mm. For every fiber embedment nine different fiber orientations were investigated. In the framework of present investigation, experimental data of

Fig. 6: a) The sample for fiber pull-out experiments, where α –inclination angle and $L/2$ – half of length of fiber immersed into the concrete matrix. b) Averaged force - pulled out length values for fiber embedded at depth 15mm.

pull-out resistance for the fiber inclined at different angle to applied pulling out force were experimentally obtained (in figure 6 are shown data for each curve, averaged over nine samples).

4 CRACKED BEAM UNDER BENDING NUMERICAL MODELING

Each macro-crack opening is governing by the pull-out process of fibers which are bridging the crack. For one particular layered prism according to fibers concentration in every ply Monte Carlo simulation was used to obtain fibers location and spatial orientations (3 coordinates of position of midpoint of each fiber and its 3 spatial inclination angles). Then the weakest plane was recognized as a

plane which is crossing lowest number of fibers. Weakest plane in the model was the plane of future macro-crack. Increasing applied loads macro-crack started to open. Each fiber which was crossed this crack started to pull out by the shortest end embedded into the concrete. Each single fiber pull-out force depending of this particular fiber current pull-out length was obtained from experimental pull-out diagrams (see figure 6 b and figure 7). Summarized over all fibers (which are crossing the crack) current load was calculated in dependence of crack opening displacement. In such way load – deflection diagrams were calculated for beams corresponded to every fabricated experimentally layered fiberconcrete beams group.

Fig. 7: Numerical modelling steps: a) Fibers geometrical modelling in the beam. Crack plane recognition. b) Crack opening simulation. Summarized over all fibers, which are crossing the crack, pull-out force calculation using single fiber pull-out tests data base. c) External loads values calculation.

5 RESULTS ANALYSIS

Numerical modelling results were compared with experimentally obtained data. Mechanical

Fig. 8: Numerical modelling results comparison with experimental data for all eight groups.

behavior of majority of layered prisms was successfully described by elaborated model. Worst results were obtained for the group 8. Additional fracture surface analysis shown that in the case of group 8 was changed failure mechanism – in the framework of the layer with fibers pulled out fibers were covered by a concrete and were pulled out as a blocks. As an explanation of the such phenomena may be relatively high fibers concentration (240kg/m^3) within this ply.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Different types of fiberconcrete beams having non-homogeneous fibers distribution in the concrete volume were fabricated and investigated. According to the performed bending tests, specimens with homogeneous chaotic fibers distribution in the sample volume were shown lowest average load bearing capacity at the crack forming and opening stage comparing with the specimens which were had non-homogeneous distribution of fibers. Detailed numerical model was elaborated. Modelling results were allowed to recognize failure mechanism change according to fibers content increase in the material.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. N. Balaguru and S. P. Shah, *Fiber-Reinforced Cement Composites*. McGraw-Hill, 1992, p. 530.
- [2] A. E. Naaman, *High-Performance Construction Materials*, no. 5. Singapore: World Scientific, 2008, pp. 91–153.
- [3] V. C. Li, *On Engineered Cementitious Composites (ECC)*. A Review of the Material and Its Applications, *J. Adv. Concr. Technol.*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2003, pp. 215–230.
- [4] C. Y. Li and B. Mobasher, Finite Element Simulations of Fiber Pull-Out Toughening in Fiber Reinforced Cement Based Composites, *Adv. Cem. Based Mater.*, vol. 7, no. 3–4, 1998, pp. 123–132.
- [5] B. Mobasher and C. Y. Li, Modeling of Stiffness Degradation of the Interfacial Zone During Fiber Debonding, *Compos. Eng.*, vol. 5, no. 10–11, 1995, pp. 1349–1365.
- [6] A. E. Naaman and H. W. Reinhardt, Proposed Classification of HPFRC Composites Based on Their Tensile Response, *Mater. Struct.*, vol. 39, no. 5, 2006, pp. 547–555.
- [7] V. Lapsa, A. Krasnikovs and K. Strauts, Fiberconcrete Non-Homogeneous Structure Element Building Technology Process and Equipment, 20.04.2011, *Latvian invention patent* LV14257.
- [8] V. Lusis, V. Lapsa and A. Krasnikovs, Method for Oriented Reinforcement of Fiberconcrete Structures Prior to Concreting, 20.06.2013, *Latvian invention patent* LV14667.
- [9] V. Lusis and A. Krasnikovs, Concrete and Fiberconcrete Construction Reinforcement Technology, 20.07.2013, *Latvian invention patent* LV14684.
- [10] P. Robins, S. Austin and P. Jones, Pull-out Behavior of Hooked Steel Fibers. *Materials and Structures*, Vol. 35, pp.434-442.
- [11] Ts Ng, Tns Htut and S. Foster, Fracture of Steel Fibre Reinforced Concrete – the Unified variable Engagement Model. UNICIV REPORT No. R-460 May 2012, The University of new South wales Sydney 2052 Australia, <http://www.civeng.unsw.edu.au>, ISBN: 85841 427 9
- [12] A. Krasnikovs and O. Kononova, Strength Prediction for Concrete Reinforced by Different Length and Shape Short Steel Fibers// *Sc. Proceedings of Riga Technical University. Transport and Engineering*, 6, vol. 31, 2009, pp.89-93.
- [13] K. Georgiadi-Stefanidi, E. Mistakidis, D. Pantousa and M. Zygomalas, Numerical Modeling of the Pull-out of Hooked Steel Fibers From High-strength Cementitious Matrix, Supplemented by Experimental Results// *Constr. Build. Mater.* 24, 2010, pp. 2489-2506.
- [14] A. Krasnikovs, A. Khabaz, I. Telnova, A. Machanovsky and J. Klavinsh, Numerical 3D Investigation of Non-metallic (glass, carbon) Fiber Pull-out Micromechanics (in concrete matrix)// *Sc. Proceedings of Riga Technical University, Transport and engineering*, 6, vol.33, 2010, pp.103-108.